

A Study of the Complexes of Inorganic Salts with Organic Bases

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Magnetic susceptibilities of complexes of zinc chloride, cadmium chloride, and mercuric chloride with pyridine and substituted pyridines have been measured by Gouy's method. These values have been compared with the computed ones, obtained by adding the experimental molar susceptibilities of the components, assuming strict additivity. The deviations from additivity have been discussed in the light of Van Vleck's equation for the molar susceptibility of polyatomic molecule.

In continuation with our previous work¹, the present communication deals with the study of the metal complexes of pyridine and substituted pyridines by magnetic method.

EXPERIMENTAL

The organic bases and the inorganic salts used for the preparation of the complexes were either B.D.H. AnalaR grade or Merck's extra pure quality and were prepared by following the method suggested by Lang². The purity of the compounds was checked by usual methods. Magnetic susceptibilities of these complexes and their components were measured by a modified form of Gouy's balance, described by Prasad and co-workers³. In Tables I and II are presented the values of specific (χ) and molar (χ_m) susceptibilities of the components and the complexes of inorganic salts with organic bases, the values being expressed in -1×10^{-6} c.g.s. units.

TABLE I

Magnetic susceptibilities of the components ($-\chi \times 10^{-6}$).

Compound.	χ .	χ_m .	Compound.	χ .	χ_m .
Zinc chloride	..	65.01	β -Picoline	0.668	62.20
Cadmium chloride	0.385	70.58	γ -Picoline	0.664	61.53
Mercuric chloride	0.298	80.92	2,4-Lutidine	0.682	73.08
Pyridine	0.632	49.93	2,6-Lutidine	0.682	73.08
α -Picoline	0.657	61.18	<i>sym</i> -Collidine	0.687	63.12

1. Sonalkar and Datar, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1960-61, 29, 48.

2. *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1578.

3. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1944, 20A, 224.

TABLE II

Magnetic susceptibilities and % deviations from additivity for complexes.

Complex.	χ .	χ_m . (obs.)	χ_m' . (calc.)	$\Delta\chi_m$ ($\chi_m - \chi_m'$).	% $\Delta\chi_m$.
A. With zinc chloride.					
Dipyridine	0.517	152.15	164.87	-12.72	- 8.36
Di- α -picoline	0.521	168.04	187.37	-19.33	-11.50
Di- β -picoline	0.530	170.94	199.41	-18.47	-10.90
Di- γ -picoline	0.523	168.69	188.67	-19.98	-11.84
Di-2,4-lutidine	0.518	181.61	211.17	-29.56	-16.28
Di-2,6-lutidine	0.510	191.96	211.17	-29.21	-16.05
<i>sym</i> -collidine	0.522	197.66	231.25	-33.59	-16.99
B. With cadmium chloride.					
Dipyridine	0.466	159.06	170.44	-11.38	-7.15
Mono- α -picoline	0.454	125.51	131.76	-6.25	-4.98
Di- β -picoline	0.482	178.13	194.98	-16.85	-9.46
Di- γ -picoline	0.477	176.28	194.24	-17.96	-10.19
Mono-2,4-lutidine	0.457	132.75	143.66	-10.91	-8.22
Mono-2,6-lutidine	0.460	133.62	143.66	-10.04	-7.51
Mono- <i>sym</i> -collidine	0.459	139.77	153.70	-13.93	-9.97
C. With mercuric chloride.					
Monopyridine	0.360	126.19	130.85	-4.67	-3.70
Mono- α -picoline	0.372	135.67	142.10	-6.43	-4.74
Mono- β -picoline	0.374	136.40	143.12	-6.72	-4.93
Mono- γ -picoline	0.373	136.03	142.75	-6.72	-4.94
Mono-2,4-lutidine	0.378	143.15	154.00	-10.85	-7.58
Mono-2,6-lutidine	0.381	144.28	154.00	-9.72	-6.74
Mono- <i>sym</i> -collidine	0.387	151.97	164.04	-12.07	-7.94

DISCUSSION

For the sake of comparison, the molar magnetic susceptibilities of these complexes were calculated from the knowledge of the experimental values of the susceptibilities of their components, assuming strict additivity. Magnetic susceptibilities of organic ligands and the inorganic salts, required for this purpose, were measured in this laboratory as there was no consistency in the values reported by different investigators for the same compounds. Attempts made in the laboratory to measure magnetic susceptibility of anhydrous zinc chloride failed as the sample absorbed moisture during packing and measurements. The value reported by Craw and Rogers⁴ has been used for these calculations. This value appears to be reliable as special precautions were taken by these authors to prepare the anhydrous salt in the pure state. The computed values of molar susceptibilities of the complexes are shown in column 4 of Table II. The percentage deviation from additivity is shown in column 6 of the same table. The observed values are apparently lower than their computed ones and therefore deviate from additivity. Since Gouy's method provides results to 1% accuracy⁵, the observed deviations are quite significant.

4. Craw and Rogers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 217.

5. Selwood, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience Publishers, 1943, p. 4.

According to Van Vleck, the susceptibility of a polyatomic molecule without a resultant spin is given by the equation:

$$\chi_m = \chi_d + \chi_p$$

where χ_d represents the diamagnetic term and is a function of Σr^2 , the radius of all electronic orbits in the molecule, and the χ_p term represents the second order paramagnetism, independent of temperature, which arises on account of the mixing of the ground and excited states of electrons in the molecule. If the metal-nitrogen bond in the complex is strong, the associating units will come very close to the metal atom, thus decreasing the value of Σr^2 and hence that of the diamagnetic susceptibility of the molecule (χ_d). In addition, this type of bonding is also likely to affect the symmetry of the component molecule. It is known that two geometrical configurations are possible for co-ordination number four: (i) a regular tetrahedron and (ii) square planar respectively, involving sp^3 and dsp^2 hybridisations. In the context of the present investigation, the latter type falls out of reckoning because d -orbital is not available for complexing the Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , and Hg^{2+} ions possessing d electronic configuration⁶. Since the complexes of zinc chloride are similar to the ammine complexes of zinc with the formula $ZnCl_2 \cdot 2NH_3$, for which a tetrahedral structure has been established from X-ray data⁶, it is reasonable to assume that these complexes possess tetrahedral configuration which makes use of sp^3 orbitals of the metal atom. According to Pople⁷, the χ_p term, which affects both diamagnetic susceptibility and the nuclear magnetic resonance shift, is quite important when p orbitals are used for the bond formation. The use of sp^3 orbitals will therefore result in a significant contribution to the χ_p term and consequently a reduction in the molar susceptibility of the complex. The observed deviations from additivity may be ascribed to the changes in χ_d and χ_p terms. Since χ_d and χ_p terms have opposite signs, the deviation from additivity is the net result of the two opposing effects. The change in the χ_p term would be more significant since the symmetry of the complex may be entirely different from that of the constituent molecules.

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6. MacGillavry and Bijvoet, *Z. Krist.*, 1936, 94, 249.

7. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1957, 239A, 541,550.